

Reflecting on Key Performance Indicators for Research Data Management Initiatives

A TRIZ Liberating Structures Workshop to kickstart an open and constructive dialogue

Tobias Hamann¹

¹Chair of Production Metrology and Quality Management & Institute for Information Management in Mechanical Engineering (Prof. Robert Schmitt), RWTH Aachen University, Aachen, Germany

²Specialised Information Service for Mobility and Transport Research (FID move), Dresden, Germany

³Saxon State and University Library Dresden (SLUB), Dresden, Germany

⁴IT Center, RWTH Aachen University, Aachen, Germany

⁵Fraunhofer-Institut für Produktionstechnologie IPT, Aachen, Germany

*Correspondence: Tobias Hamann, tobias.hamann@wzl-iqs.rwth-aachen.de

Abstract

For NFDI4ING, the first funding period of the first consortia is coming to an end in September 2025, with a possibility for a second funding period. To collect the results generated, the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) has provided NFDI4ING consortia with a supplementary data sheet, which breaks down the accomplishments of the consortia into key performance indicators (KPIs) [1]. However, some KPIs are easier tracked while some are harder to maintain. One example are KPIs for Services, as these have very different scopes and goals, which are not easily commonly measured. Additionally, some KPIs can be collected differently depending on the interpretation of the supplementary data sheet.

Unless there is a common understanding by the ones recording and evaluating KPIs, measuring activities effectively and as intended is hindered significantly. This is relevant both within NFDI4ING, as well as other NFDI consortia. Even when a common understanding of the supplementary data sheet exists within a consortium, for instance in NFDI4ING, the collection of KPIs can be challenging. Additionally, the comparability between NFDI consortia or other research initiatives is lacking. This even applies despite the fact that KPIs of DFG supplementary data sheet are primarily meant for comparison of the development of each of the consortia on themselves. Furthermore, this issue is not limited to NFDI4ING alone but also affects other research initiatives, for example DFG founded “Fachinformationsdienste für die Wissenschaft” (FID, Specialised Information Services).

CoRDI offers a unique opportunity to discuss such issues. Hence, NFDI4ING and FID move propose a common workshop to discuss the recording of KPIs in the context of research supporting initiatives. Goal of this workshop is the gathering of problems faced by participants when collecting KPIs and ideas on how to solve these problems. The workshop will follow the TRIZ Liberating Structures approach by Kubelke and Schmitt [2] and is planned for approximately 90 minutes. Firstly, participants collaboratively create a list of hurdles and challenges that would guarantee failure in reaching certain KPIs. Through this process, the participants engage in “creative destruction”, identifying counterproductive practices that are considered unspoken. This approach follows three steps:

1. **List the worst hurdles and challenges:** Together, participants brainstorm activities or hurdles to *ensure* the worst possible outcome, e.g. not reaching a single entry in a specific KPI.
2. **Identify real-life parallels:** Participants reflect honestly on current behaviours that could cause those worst-case actions.
3. **Decide what to change:** Participants determine which of these behaviours should be stopped and how to take the first steps toward doing so.

Kickstarting a reflective and constructive dialogue, the TRIZ Liberating Structures approach enables the identification of hidden dysfunctions and allows for a new and beneficial perspective on the collection of KPIs. The results will give a better understanding for all participants on how to address challenges when recording KPIs. Additionally, common problems and their solutions can give the institutions asking for KPIs an impression on how KPIs can be improved in the future.

Resources

- NFDI4Ing
 - Collaborative work in NFDI. [10.5281/zenodo.8296724](https://zenodo.org/record/8296724). An overview over the cross-consortial collaborations within the NFDI.
 - NFDI Network Analysis / NFDI Netzwerkanalyse. [10.5281/zenodo.14523867](https://zenodo.org/record/14523867). Data and Plots about the collaborative Network within NFDI.
 - Summary of NFDI4Ing Conference 2022 hosted by RWTH Aachen University. https://git.rwth-aachen.de/nfdi4ing/nfdi4ing-conference/-/blob/main/2022%20-%20RWTH%20Aachen/Summary.md?ref_type=heads. An NFDI4Ing internal documentation on the 2022 NFDI4Ing conference, the development of registrations and participations during the event and lessons learned.
 - Eigene Werke NFDI. [10.5281/zenodo.12680673](https://zenodo.org/record/12680673) A cooperation between NFDI4Ing and Text+ utilising Zotero to automatically process the metadata of their publications.
 - Progress Report NFDI4Ing. <https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/323794/7484ba3d8c944318586bf7620fe98487/nfdi4ing-data.pdf>. Intermediate report of NFDI4Ing.
- Specialised Information Services:
 - FIDplus-Indikatorik: Präambel. <https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/351704/f06e717ff44cb7fd2c34f37e3050b0c5/12-232-de-data.pdf>. FIDplus-Indicators [02/25] and guiding questions for assessment.

- Konkordanz Datenblatt FID - FIDplus. <https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/351702/8cd3d3c568610c02cfb2edcf25e43cfb/12-231-de-data.xlsx>. A data sheet to concretise the explanations in the application by providing further details based on the indicators developed for FIDplus.
- NFDI:
 - Erfahrungen mit der strukturellen Gestaltung von NFDI. [10.5281/zenodo.14867063](https://zenodo.org/record/14867063).
 - Status quo und Zukunft der NFDI - Eine Perspektive der Fachkonsortien. [10.5281/zenodo.14277470](https://zenodo.org/record/14277470).

Author contributions

- Tobias Hamann: Conceptualization, Methodology, Project administration, Software, Writing – original draft
- Matthias Fuchs: Conceptualization, Resources, Writing – review & editing
- Évariste Demandt: Data curation, Resources, Visualization, Writing – review & editing
- Anas Abdelrazeq: Writing – review & editing
- Robert Schmitt: Funding acquisition, Supervision

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

The authors would like to thank the Federal Government and the Heads of Government of the Länder, as well as the Joint Science Conference (GWK), for their funding and support within the framework of NFDI4ING consortium. Funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) – project number 442146713.

References

- [1] DFG. “Guide to filling out the Supplementary data sheet for consortia of the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI),” Accessed: Apr. 17, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.dfg.de/en/research-funding/funding-initiative/nfdi/guide-to-filling-out-the-supplementary-data-sheet-for-consortia-of-the-national-research-data-infrastructure-nfdi-%7D>.
- [2] A.-M. Kubelke and H. R. Schmitt. “TRIZ – Liberating Structures,” Accessed: Apr. 17, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://liberatingstructures.de/liberating-structures-menu/triz/%7D>.